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Research Article

DEMOCRATIC HEALTH LEADERSHIP STYLE IN ACTION

Eman.S.Almajnuni¹, Mohammed.M.Alameer², Raad.D.Alharthi³, Saleh.H.Alzahrani⁴,
Sami.N.Almughaty⁵, Wejdan.A.Arrafi⁶, Wafaa.S.Althobiti⁷, Badr.O.Alharbi⁸,
Amin.K.Almaamery⁹, Mohammad.M.Alsolmi¹⁰, Ahmed.M.Alharbi¹¹, Haneen.J.Rizq¹²,
Majed.A.Alobaidi¹³

Health Administration specialist at king Abdulaziz Hospital -Strategic management¹

Health services and hospital management specialist -head of the Quality department at the forensic
medical services center in Mecca²

Technician, center manager, at primary healthcare center in Sharia³

Health Administration and hospital specialist in health affairs in Mecca region⁴

Health Administration and hospital specialist at king Abdulaziz Hospital⁵

Health Administration and hospital specialist at king Abdulaziz Hospital⁶

Health Administration and hospital specialist at Al-Sail Al-Kabir health center⁷

Health Administration specialist at king Abdulaziz Hospital⁸

Health Administration specialist at king Abdulaziz Hospital⁹

Health Administration specialist at king Abdulaziz Hospital¹⁰

Health Administration specialist in the control department¹¹

Clinical Nutrition specialist at King Abdulaziz Hospital¹²

Health and Hospital services administration specialist at King Faisal Medical complex-financial
management- in Taif¹³

Abstract:

The study aimed to find out what is, what is the democratic leadership style in the work environment, what is the role of the democratic health leader in work, what is the role of democratic leadership in participation in work. A questionnaire was created via the Google Drive program and distributed via social media (WhatsApp) to the targeted targets, who are health practitioners in Mecca, 750 questionnaires were distributed, and 700 responses were obtained from this questionnaire.

Corresponding author:

Eman.S.Almajnuni,

Health Administration specialist at king Abdulaziz Hospital -Strategic management¹

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Leadership manner is the leader's style of directing, applying plans, and interesting people. Several authors have proposed identifying several different leadership styles as presented by leaders in political, business, or other fields. Studies on leadership method are conducted in the military, expressing a path that confirm the holistic view of leadership, containing how the physical presence of a leader locates what others see of that leader. Factors of physical presence in this context have military gait, physical fitness, confidence, and flexibility. The intellectual ability of a leader helps him conceptualize solutions and gain the knowledge to do the job. Conceptual leadership capabilities apply agility and judgment. Innovation, personal tact and domain knowledge. Domain knowledge includes tactical and technical knowledge as well as cultural and geopolitical awareness. In his article "Leadership That Gets Results," Daniel Goleman (2000) talks about six leadership styles ⁽¹⁾⁽²⁾. The democratic leadership style include of the leader sharing decision-making abilities with group members by raising the interests of group members and practicing social equality ⁽³⁾. The limits of democratic sharing tend to be constrained by the needs of the organization or group and the instrumental value of people's attributes (skills, attitudes, etc.). The democratic style contains the idea that everyone, by virtue of their human status, should play a function in group decisions. However, the democratic style of leadership still requires direction and monitoring by an appointed leader. The democratic style requests the leader to make decisions about who to invite within the group and who is given the right to participate in, make and vote on decisions ⁽⁴⁾. Research has found that this leadership style is most effective and creates higher productivity, better contributions from group members, and raised group morale. Democratic leadership can lead to better ideas and more creative solutions to problems because group members are encouraged to share their ideas. While democratic leadership is one of the most effective leadership styles, it has some potential downsides. In situations where you are Roles are unclear or time is of the essence, democratic leadership can drive to connection failures and incomplete projects. Democratic leadership works best in situations where group members are skilled and eager to share their knowledge. It is also significant to have plenty of time to permit people to contribute, develop a plan and then vote on the best course of action ⁽⁵⁾.

2-MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This study started in (the holy city of Mecca in Saudi Arabia), began writing the research and then recording the questionnaire in June 2023, and the study ended with data collection in October 2023. The researcher used the descriptive analytical approach that uses a quantitative or qualitative description of the social phenomenon (Democratic health leadership style in action). This kind of study is characterized by analysis, reason, objectivity, and reality, as it is concerned with individuals and societies, as it studies the variables and their effects on the health of the individual, society, and consumer, the spread of diseases and their relationship to demographic variables such as age, gender, nationality, and marital status. Status, occupation ⁽⁶⁾, And use the Excel 2010 Office suite histogram to arrange the results using: Frequency tables Percentages ⁽⁷⁾. A questionnaire is a remarkable and helpful tool for collecting a huge amount of data, however, researchers were not able to personally interview participants on the online survey, due to social distancing regulations at the time to prevent infection between participants and researchers and vice versa (not coronavirus participation completely disappearing from society). He only answered the questionnaire electronically, because the questionnaire consisted of eight questions, all of which were closed. The online approach has also been used to generate valid samples in similar studies in Saudi Arabia and elsewhere ⁽⁸⁾

3- RESULTS:

The percentage of those who agreed to participate in the research questionnaire was 100%, and the percentage of those aged 25-34 years was 25%, and those aged 35-44 years (also the same percentage), while those aged 45-54 years made up 50%, and those aged 55 -60 years 0%. As for their gender, they were as follows: 75% males and 25% females. As for their nationalities, they were 100% Saudi, and as for their professions, they were as follows: student 12.5%, government employee 75%, private sector employee 12.5%, housewife 0%, freelancer 0%, entrepreneur 0%. As for their educational status, it was as follows: primary 0%, middle school 0%, secondary school, doctorate holders 12.5%, university 50%, diploma 0%, and master's 25%.As for the questions and the responses to them (yes and no from the participants), their answers were as follows: The first question: Is your health leadership democratic? Yes 62.5% and no

37.5%. The second question is about: Does your leadership apply agility, judgment, innovation, personal tact, and knowledge of the field? 75% or 25%. The third question: Do you feel that your manager lets you work without pressure? Yes 87.5% and no 12.5%. The fourth question: Do you feel that your manager is a leader who shares decision-making capabilities with group members by promoting the interests of group members and practicing social equality? Yes 100%. The fifth question: Do you have a desire not to take leave from work because of your manager? Yes, 75% and no, 25%. Question Six: Does the democratic style

include the idea that everyone, by virtue of their human condition, should play a role in the decisions of the group? Yes 87.5% and no 12.5%. Question 7: Is this leadership style the most effective and creates higher productivity, better contributions from group members, and increased group morale? Yes, 75% and no, 25%. Question 8: The democratic style requires the leader to make decisions about who is to be called upon within the group and who is given the right to participate in, make and vote on decisions? Yes 87.5% and no 12.5%. (figure No.1)

Figure No.1: Opinions and attitudes of participants regarding the democratic health leadership style at work

4-DISCUSSION:

We conclude from this study that, we find, through the responses of the participants in the questionnaire, that the democratic health leadership style is considered one of the best health leadership methods, as it ensures that everyone's opinions are shared easily.

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